

Ameliorating Effect of Vitamin C on Aluminium Phosphide-Induced Toxicity in Wistar Rats

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Abstract

This study was designed to investigate the potential toxic effect of aluminium phosphide (AIP) and the protective role of vitamin C on liver, kidney and haematology biomarkers using Wistar rats. Thirty male Wistar rats were divided randomly into six groups of five animals each. Group 1 served as control and was administered distilled water. Groups 2, 5 and 6 were administered with AIP-laced diet (1.2 mg/kg) for 28 days. Groups 3, 4, 5 and 6 received vitamin C at varying doses (50 mg/kg and 100 mg/kg) also throughout the duration of the experiment. At the end of the treatments, all the rats were sacrificed and blood samples collected. Serum biomarkers and haematology markers were assayed. Data collected were analyzed using student t-test and ANOVA. Vitamin C significantly ($P < 0.05$) reversed AIP-induced alterations in liver function parameters with ALT, AST, ALP and bilirubin levels reduced by 6.3%, 14.9%, 9.8% and 13.4%. Albumin and total protein levels increased by 9.8% and 13.4%. Alterations in kidney function indices were also significantly ($P < 0.05$) reversed with creatinine, urea, sodium, potassium and chloride levels reduced by 20.3%, 36.2%, 4.7%, 4.9% and 37.4%. Also the alterations observed in haematological indices were significantly ($P < 0.05$) reversed with red blood cells, hemoglobin and hematocrit levels increased by 15.4%, 15.3% and 13%. White blood cells, lymphocyte, neutrophils and platelet levels reduced by 14.6%, 5.5%, 21.4% and 14.3% respectively. Vitamin C can therefore be inferred to be protective against AIP toxicity and could potentially serve as an agent against its poisoning.

Keywords: Aluminium phosphide, Haematological parameters, Kidney injury, Liver injury, Vitamin C

1.0 Introduction

Throughout the last decades, the rising demand of food safety has inspired researchers about the risk related to the use of food contaminated with pesticides, heavy metals or toxins [1]. For many years, pesticide poisoning has been regarded a significant public health issue [2]. According to a review published in 2020 [3], 385 million unintentional pesticide poisonings were reported each year, resulting in 300,000 deaths globally. Aluminium phosphide (AIP) is a commonly used pesticide and rodenticide. It has been implicated in many accidental and suicidal poisoning cases, especially in developing countries [4]. AIP is available in the form of tablets or pellets with brand names like Celphos, Alphos etc. [5, 6]. The toxicity

of AIP arises from the phosphine gas it generates on contact with moisture and hydrochloric acid in the stomach [7]. Phosphine inhibits the cytochrome oxidase enzyme system, leading to cellular hypoxia, organ dysfunction and acidosis [8]. The liver and kidneys are most commonly affected, with hepatotoxicity seen in over 97% of poisoning cases, manifesting as jaundice, hepatomegaly, centrilobular necrosis and liver cell degeneration. About 73% of patients show evidence of acute kidney injury, with symptoms like hematuria, proteinuria and rising serum creatinine levels [9].

Vitamin C or ascorbic acid is an essential water-soluble micronutrient that must be obtained from dietary sources in humans due to a lack of L-gulonolactone oxidase, the enzyme required for its

biosynthesis [10, 11]. Vitamin C acts as a potent antioxidant in the body by virtue of its ability to donate electrons. It can directly scavenge an array of reactive oxygen and nitrogen species like superoxide, hydrogen peroxide, hydroxyl radicals, singlet oxygen, peroxynitrite and hypochlorous acid [12]. Vitamin C also assists in recycling other important antioxidants like vitamin E and glutathione back to their active states [13, 14]. Despite growing evidence of AIP toxicity, there is still no known antidote against its poisoning and limited studies have explored the protective effects of vitamin C in a controlled experimental setting. Hence, this study aims to investigate the protective property of vitamin C against AIP induced toxicity in the liver, kidney and blood of wistar rats.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Experimental Animals

Thirty (30) Wistar strain adult male albino rats (160 ± 10 g) were purchased from National Veterinary Research Institute, Vom, Plateau State, Nigeria in October, 2024. The rats were initially acclimatized for a period of two week after their purchase. They were kept in a well-ventilated animal house and fed with vital feeds purchased from Grand Cereals Limited, Nigeria, and with unlimited supply of water. They were also subjected to natural photo period of about 12 hours light and 12 hours dark cycle daily throughout the duration of the study.

2.3 Experimental Design

The 30 rats were divided randomly into six groups of five animals each. The rats in group 1 served as control and were administered distilled water. Groups 2, 5 and 6 were administered with AIP laced diet (1.2 mg/kg) for 28 days. Rats in Groups 3, 4, 5 and 6 received vitamin C at varying doses (50 mg/kg and 100 mg/kg) also throughout the duration of the experiment as outlined below. At the end of the 28 days duration of the study, all the rats were sacrificed.

- Groups 1: Normal control
- Groups 2: AIP (1.2 mg/kg)
- Groups 3: Vitamin C (50 mg/kg)
- Groups 4: Vitamin C (100 mg/kg)
- Groups 5: AIP (1.2 mg/kg) + Vitamin C (50 mg/kg)
- Groups 6: AIP (1.2 mg/kg) + Vitamin C (100 mg/kg)

2.4 Sample Collection and Preparation

At the end of the experimental period, the rats were fasted overnight. Blood samples were collected into plain tubes for biochemical analysis and heparinized tubes for haematological analysis, via retro-orbital plexus with capillary tubes. The rats were later sacrificed by cervical dislocation. The blood samples collected into plain tubes were later centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes and the supernatant were decanted into labeled tubes and stored at -20°C for biochemical analysis.

2.5 Biochemical and Haematological Analysis

Liver function indices such as alanine aminotransferase (ALT) and aspartate aminotransferase (AST) [15], alkaline phosphatase (ALP) [16], total bilirubin [17], serum albumin [18] and total protein [19] were assayed. Kidney function parameters such as urea level [20], creatinine [21], serum sodium (Na^+) [22], potassium (K^+) [23] and chloride (Cl^-) [24] were also determined. The liver and kidney function parameters were measured spectrophotometrically using commercially available assay kits (Randox Laboratories, UK) following manufacturer protocols. The determination of haematological parameters was done using the ABACUS 380 Automated Haematology Analyser.

2.6 Data Analysis

SPSS version 27 was used for the data analysis and the results were expressed as Means \pm standard deviation (SD). The significance of differences between groups was calculated by using student's t-test and ANOVA. A p-value of less than 0.05 ($P < 0.05$) was considered statistically significant.

3.0 Results

3.1 Biochemical indicator of Hepatic Functions

In Table 1, administration of AIP caused a significant ($P < 0.05$) elevation in the serum activities of ALT (249.00 ± 14.00), AST (288.33 ± 16.07) and ALP (717.00 ± 8.49); significant ($P < 0.05$) depletion in the serum concentrations of albumin (20.95 ± 1.20) and total protein (38.50 ± 0.71); and elevation in the concentration of bilirubin (1.42 ± 0.09) when compared with the normal control. But co-administration of AIP and vitamin C led to a significant ($P < 0.05$) decrease in the serum activities

of ALT (225.00±2.65), AST (245.00±8.18) and ALP (647.00±16.70); significant (P<0.05) elevation in the serum concentrations of albumin (23.13±0.71) and

total protein (44.50±0.71); and decrease in the concentration of bilirubin (1.23±0.01) when compared with the AIP treated animals.

Table 1: Levels of Liver Function markers in male Wistar rats treated with AIP and Vitamin C

Groups	ALT (U/L)	AST (U/L)	ALP (U/L)	ALB (g/dl)	T.PRT (g/dl)	T.BIL (g/dl)
1: Normal control	210.67±6.02	240.00±8.19	555.50±21.92	24.55±0.07	48.00±1.73	1.10±0.14
2: AIP (1.2 mg/kg)	249.00±14.00*	288.33±16.07*	717.00±8.49*	20.95±1.20*	38.50±0.71*	1.42±0.09*
3: Vit. C (50 mg/kg)	207.67±6.81	236.33±25.15	549.67±7.09	24.53±1.97	47.67±1.53	1.13±0.40
4: Vit. C (100 mg/kg)	201.00±10.15	232.33±20.50	542.67±13.20	26.90±1.68	48.67±2.08	1.02±0.18
5: AIP (1.2 mg/kg) + Vit. C (50 mg/kg)	233.33±5.86**	252.00±5.20**	651.33±21.03**	22.83±0.38**	43.67±0.58**	1.30±0.06
6: AIP (1.2 mg/kg) + Vit. C (100 mg/kg)	225.00±2.65**	245.00±8.18**	647.00±16.70**	23.13±0.71**	44.50±0.71**	1.23±0.01**

Values are expressed as mean ± standard deviation (N = 5); * Significantly different from normal control (P<0.05); ** Significantly different from AIP alone treated group (P<0.05); AIP= Aluminium phosphide, Vit. C= Vitamin C, ALT= Alanine amino transferase, AST= Aspartate amino transferase, ALP= Alkaline phosphatase, ALB= Albumin, T.PRT= Total Protein, T.BIL= Total Bilirubin

3.2 Biochemical indicator of Kidney Functions

In Table 2, administration of AIP caused a significant (P<0.05) elevation in the serum concentrations of urea (9.35±0.49), creatinine (277.25±38.54), sodium (157.33±2.08), potassium (14.40±0.57) and chloride

(107.50±2.12) when compared with the normal control. But co-administration of AIP and Vitamin C led to a significant (P<0.05) decrease in the serum concentrations of urea (7.45±0.49), creatinine (176.84±13.68), sodium (150.00±2.00), potassium (11.45±0.64) and chloride (103.33±1.53) when compared with the AIP treated animals.

Table 2: Levels of Kidney function markers in male Wistar rats treated with AIP and Vitamin C

Groups	Urea (mmol/L)	Creatinine (µmol/L)	Na ⁺ (mmol/L)	K ⁺ (mmol/L)	Cl ⁻ (mmol/L)
1: Normal control	6.97±1.27	105.17±8.25	151.70±0.42	10.84±0.02	100.87±1.50
2: AIP (1.2 mg/kg)	9.35±0.49*	277.25±38.54*	157.33±2.08*	14.40±0.57*	107.50±2.12*
3: Vit. C (50 mg/kg)	6.23±0.06	97.15±5.04	151.00±3.00	10.60±0.57	101.67±2.52
4: Vit. C (100 mg/kg)	6.10±0.10	96.67±6.79	147.10±4.43	8.45±1.63	99.33±1.53
5: AIP (1.2 mg/kg) + Vit. C (50 mg/kg)	7.50±0.26**	183.67±14.37**	152.67±1.53**	13.70±0.42	104.33±2.08**
6: AIP (1.2 mg/kg) + Vit. C (100 mg/kg)	7.45±0.49**	176.84±13.68**	150.00±2.00**	11.45±0.64*	103.33±1.53**

Values are expressed as mean ± standard deviation (N = 5); * Significantly different from normal control (P<0.05); ** Significantly different from AIP alone treated group (P<0.05); AIP= Aluminium phosphide, Vit. C= Vitamin C

3.3 Haematological Parameters

In Table 3, administration of AIP caused a significant (P<0.05) elevation in the blood levels of white blood cells (28.33±2.14), lymphocyte (86.60±1.98), neutrophils (25.67±1.33), platelet (534.5±4.95), red cell distribution width-standard deviation (43.37±1.78), red cell distribution width - coefficient of variation (22.70±0.80) and mean corpuscular volume (65.20±3.81). Also significant (P<0.05) decrease in the blood levels of red blood cells

(6.02±0.58), hemoglobin (11.25±0.21), hematocrit (35.83±1.80), platelet distribution width (12.95±1.48), mean platelet volume (7.95±0.07), platelet-large cell ratio (24.75±0.92), mean corpuscular hemoglobin (16.67±0.55), mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration (29.47±0.87), when compared with the normal control. But co-administration of AIP and Vitamin C led to a significant (P<0.05) decrease in the blood levels of white blood cells (24.20±3.55), lymphocyte

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(81.8±1.90), neutrophils (20.17±2.54), platelet (458.33±36.95), red cell distribution width-standard deviation (38.10±0.52), red cell distribution width - coefficient of variation (18.77±1.62). Also significant (P<0.05) increase in red blood cells (6.95±0.17), hemoglobin (12.97±0.76), hematocrit (40.50±2.27), platelet distribution width

(15.2±0.17), mean platelet volume (9.77±0.92), platelet-large cell ratio (31.33±1.37), mean corpuscular volume (57.2±1.91), mean corpuscular hemoglobin (17.87±0.12), mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration (31.7±1.47), dose dependently when compared with the AIP treated animals.

Table 3: Levels of Haematological parameters in male Wistar rats treated with AIP and Vitamin C

Parameters/Groups	1: Normal control	2: AIP (1.2 mg/kg)	3: Vit. C (50 mg/kg)	4: Vit. C (100 mg/kg)	5: AIP (1.2 mg/kg) + Vit. C (50 mg/kg)	6: AIP (1.2 mg/kg) + Vit. C (100 mg/kg)
WBC (x10 ⁹ /L)	20.6±1.93	28.33±2.14*	19.25±1.48	18.87±0.38	24.67±1.36**	24.20±3.55**
LYM (x10 ⁹ /L)	78.25±0.35	86.60±1.98*	72.53±2.40	72.37±4.27	82.63±1.05**	81.8±1.90**
NEUT (x10 ⁹ /L)	12.07±1.27	25.67±1.33*	11.25±1.76	10.25±0.64	20.23±1.07**	20.17±2.54**
RBC (x10 ¹² /L)	7.72±0.92	6.02±0.58*	7.71±0.08	7.90±0.15	6.83±0.06**	6.95±0.17**
HGB (g/L)	14.63±0.40	11.25±0.21*	14.50±0.53	15.07±0.75	12.70±0.61**	12.97±0.76**
HCT (%)	43.53±5.14	35.83±1.80*	43.97±1.61	44.53±2.93	38.93±1.16**	40.50±2.27**
PLT (x10 ⁹ /L)	342±28.28	534.5±4.95*	339.33±10.01	332.50±7.78	490.00±36.34	458.33±36.95**
RDW SD (%)	33.53±1.63	43.37±1.78*	33.77±1.66	32.70±1.30	40.83±1.70	38.10±0.52**
RDW CV (%)	16.23±1.10	22.70±0.80*	16.17±2.03	15.47±0.64	21.57±0.57	18.77±1.62**
PDW (µm)	17.65±0.78	12.95±1.48*	18.13±0.68	18.2±1.00	14.00±0.53	15.2±0.17**
MPV (fL)	11.1±0.28	7.95±0.07*	11.30±0.62	11.87±0.75	8.4±0.10**	9.77±0.92**
P-LCR (fL)	42.13±2.69	24.75±0.92*	44.40±6.51	45.43±2.50	28.43±10.11	31.33±1.37**
MCV (fL)	55.83±1.07	65.20±3.81*	54.90±1.73	53.50±1.61	59.8±2.60	57.2±1.91**
MCH (pg)	18.10±0.17	16.67±0.55*	18.6±0.85	18.63±0.67	17.85±0.21**	17.87±0.12**
MCHC (g/L)	32.63±0.47	29.47±0.87*	32.87±0.86	33.50±0.90	30.07±0.83	31.7±1.47**

Values are expressed as mean ± standard deviation (N = 5); * Significantly different from normal control (P<0.05); ** Significantly different from AIP alone treated group (P<0.05); AIP= Aluminium phosphide, Vit. C= Vitamin C, WBC= White blood cells, LYM= Lymphocyte, NEUT= Neutrophils, RBC= Red blood cells, HGB= Hemoglobin, HCT= Hematocrit, PLT= Platelet, RDW- SD= Red cell distribution width-standard deviation, RDW - CV= Red cell distribution width - coefficient of variation, PDW= Platelet distribution width, MPV= Mean platelet volume, P-LCR= Platelet-large cell ratio, MCV= Mean corpuscular volume, MCH= Mean corpuscular hemoglobin and MCHC= Mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration.

4.0 Discussion

The most common enzymes employed as indicators of hepatocellular damage are the transaminase enzymes (Aspartate aminotransferase; AST and Alanine aminotransferase; ALT) and alkaline phosphatase. Damage to the liver results in increase in their activities in the plasma. Increases in serum enzyme activities are roughly proportional to the extent of tissue damage [25]. In this study, the results from ALT, AST and ALP showed that administration of AIP caused a significant elevation

in the serum activities of ALT, AST and ALP when compared with the control. The elevated serum levels of these hepatic markers have been attributed to liver injury, because these enzymes are normally located in cytoplasmic area of the cell and are released into circulation in case of cellular damage [26, 27]. Vitamin C, when co-administered with AIP was however able to modulate significantly the AIP induced liver injuries by lowering the activity of ALT, AST and ALP.

Albumin is a protein made specifically by the liver. It is the main constituent of total protein (the remaining from globulins). Albumin levels are depleted in liver injury and chronic disease, such as cirrhosis. It is also depleted in nephrotic syndrome, where it is lost through the urine [25]. The consequence of low albumin can be edema since the intravascular oncotic pressure becomes lower than the extravascular space [28]. From this study, AIP caused a significant depletion in the serum concentration of albumin and total protein but vitamin C when co-administered with AIP was able to ameliorate the effect.

Bilirubin is an endogenous anion derived from hemoglobin degradation from the red blood cells. When the liver function tests are abnormal and the serum bilirubin levels are high, it suggests underlying liver injury or disease [29]. The administration of AIP caused a significant elevation in the concentration of bilirubin but co-administration of AIP and Vitamin C led to a significant reduction in its concentration dose dependently.

Serum urea, creatinine and electrolytes (sodium, potassium, and chloride) may be indicated in acute renal failure, prerenal failure, renal dialysis and decreased glomerular filtration rate [30]. Increase serum urea, creatinine and electrolytes are the major biochemical biomarkers in measuring abnormal kidney function [31]. The administration of AIP led to a significant elevation in the serum concentration of urea, creatinine, sodium, potassium and chloride but co-administration of AIP and Vitamin C was able to modulate the effect which led to a significant decrease in the serum concentration of urea, creatinine, sodium, chloride and potassium.

Haematological parameters are valuable indicators of toxicity because they reflect how the body responds to exposure to harmful substances [32]. Changes in these parameters can signal tissue damage, oxidative stress, and alterations in immune function, making them useful for assessing the effects of toxic substances in biological systems [33]. Previous studies have shown that exposure to chemicals like pesticides can alter hematological parameters in animals [34] and humans [35]. This study showed that the administration of AIP caused a significant elevation in the blood levels of white blood cells, lymphocyte and neutrophils. Also elevated were the levels of platelet, red cell distribution width-standard deviation, red cell

distribution width - coefficient of variation and mean corpuscular volume. AIP administration also caused significant decrease in the levels of red blood cells, hemoglobin, hematocrit, platelet distribution width and mean platelet volume. There are also significant decrease in platelet-large cell ratio, mean corpuscular hemoglobin and mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration. However, co-administration of AIP and Vitamin C dose dependently led to a significant modulation of the various alterations observed.

5.0 Conclusion

This study revealed that AIP phosphide altered the liver function, caused renal and haematological alterations. There is significant elevation in the liver enzymes, total bilirubin, creatinine, urea, sodium, potassium and chloride, with subsequent reduction in albumin and total protein concentrations. White blood cells, lymphocyte, neutrophils, platelet, red cell distribution width-standard deviation, red cell distribution width - coefficient of variation, mean corpuscular volume, were significantly elevated. Red blood cells, hemoglobin, hematocrit, platelet distribution width, mean platelet volume, platelet-large cell ratio, mean corpuscular hemoglobin and mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration, were significantly depleted. From the study however, vitamin C was able to significantly ameliorate AIP induced toxicity dose dependently. Vitamin C can therefore be inferred to be protective against these AIP induced toxicities and could potentially serve as a potent agent against its poisoning.

6.0 Conflict of interest

The authors have no conflict of interest to declare.

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